

Supplementary Information (SI) for

“Do Climate Extremes Result in More Ambitious Mitigation and Adaptation Climate Policy?”

SI-Section A: Narrative Literature Review

The primary objective of our narrative literature review was to qualitatively synthesize and illustrate the main findings from the existing literature on how climate extremes influence the stringency and design of mitigation and adaptation policies, as well as the political mechanisms through which these events impact policy outcomes. Unlike a full systematic review, our narrative review does not directly follow the PRISMA guidelines for systematic reviews but seeks to provide a broader overview of the available research on this topic, identify knowledge gaps, and map the scope, range, and nature of the existing evidence. To conduct the scoping review, we used the following search strings across Google Scholar, Web of Science, and Scopus. Additionally, we screened forward and backward citations of the identified papers to ensure comprehensive coverage. We cited the key identified studies in our manuscript.

Google Scholar:

("climate extremes" OR "extreme weather events" OR "climate change") AND ("climate policy" OR "climate politics" OR "media discourses" OR "social media" OR "public opinion" OR "voting behavior" OR "interest groups" OR "political parties" OR "social movements" OR "policy adoption" OR "policy design" OR "policy stringency") AND ("mitigation" OR "adaptation")

Web of Science:

TS=("climate extremes" OR "extreme weather events" OR "climate change") AND ("climate policy" OR "climate politics" OR "media discourses" OR "social media" OR "public opinion" OR "voting behavior" OR "interest groups" OR "political parties" OR "social movements" OR "policy adoption" OR "policy design" OR "policy stringency") AND ("mitigation" OR "adaptation")) AND Document Types=(Article) AND Languages=(English)

Scopus:

TITLE-ABS-KEY(("climate extremes" OR "extreme weather events" OR "climate change") AND ("climate policy" OR "climate politics" OR "media discourses" OR "social media" OR "public opinion" OR "voting behavior" OR "interest groups" OR "political parties" OR "social movements" OR "policy adoption" OR "policy design" OR "policy stringency") AND ("mitigation" OR "adaptation")) AND (LIMIT-TO(DOCTYPE, "ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO(LANGUAGE, "English)

In addition, to illustrate the critical gap of studies on the effects of climate extremes in developing country contexts, we used the following search strings across Google Scholar, Web of Science, and Scopus and discussed the results from the limited number of relevant identified studies in our manuscript.

Google Scholar:

("climate extreme" OR "climate hazard" OR "extreme weather" OR "climate shock" OR "natural disaster" OR "climate risk" OR "extreme temperature" OR heatwave OR drought OR flood OR hurricane OR storm OR wildfire OR landslide OR typhoon OR cyclone OR tornado OR "climate-related disaster")

AND

("policy adoption" OR "policy implementation" OR "policy change" OR "policy feedback" OR "policy diffusion" OR "political feasibility" OR "policy transition")

AND

("developing country" OR "Global South" OR "low-income country" OR "lower-middle-income country" OR "least developed country" OR "emerging economy" OR "emerging economies" OR Africa OR "Sub-Saharan Africa" OR "South America" OR "Latin America" OR "Central America" OR Asia OR "South Asia" OR "Southeast Asia" OR Indochina OR "Middle East and North Africa" OR MENA)

Web of Science:

("climate extreme*" OR "climate hazard*" OR "extreme weather" OR "climate shock*" OR "natural disaster*" OR "climate risk*" OR "extreme temperature*" OR "heatwave*" OR "drought*" OR "flood*" OR "hurricane*" OR "storm*" OR "wildfire*" OR "landslide*" OR "typhoon*" OR "cyclone*" OR "tornado*" OR "climate-related disaster*")

AND

("policy adoption" OR "policy implementation" OR "policy change*" OR "policy feedback" OR "policy diffusion" OR "political feasibility" OR "policy transition*")

AND

("developing countr*" OR "Global South" OR "low-income countr*" OR "lower-middle-income countr*" OR "least developed countr*" OR "emerging economy" OR "emerging economies" OR "Africa" OR "Sub-Saharan Africa" OR "South America" OR "Latin America" OR "Central America" OR "Asia" OR "South Asia" OR "Southeast Asia" OR "Indochina" OR "Middle East and North Africa" OR "MENA")

Scopus:

TITLE-ABS-KEY("climate extreme*" OR "climate hazard*" OR "extreme weather" OR "climate shock*" OR "natural disaster*" OR "climate risk*" OR "extreme temperature*" OR heatwave* OR drought* OR flood* OR hurricane* OR storm* OR wildfire* OR landslide* OR typhoon* OR cyclone* OR tornado* OR "climate-related disaster*")

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SI-Section B: Panel Regression

Data

We take the OECD's Climate Actions and Policies Measurement Framework (CAPMF) data from Stechemesser et al.¹ which covers 51 countries from 1990 to 2022. For the United States, data is only available for 2000-2020. As a dependent variable, we use the average stringency value of all policy areas in the CAPMF database per country and year. As an alternative dependent variable, we follow Nachtigall et al.² in averaging stringency for each of the different modules in the CAPMF (buildings, electricity, transport, industry, cross-sectoral policies, and international climate policy) and then weighting each module equally.

For climate indicators, we take country-level, annual indicators from the OECD's database³ on exposure to climate-related hazards for annual temperature and annual precipitation (both as anomalies over the 1981-2010 baseline period), year-on-year soil moisture change, the number of days with very strong heat stress (i.e., over 38°C), and the share of land exposed to extreme precipitation (defined as daily precipitation exceeding the historical 99th percentile over the baseline period). As additional indicators used in robustness checks, we also take the percentage of the population exposed to wildfire danger and, as alternative measures of extreme heat, the number of hot summer days and the number of very hot days (defined as exceeding the historical 95th percentile). For more information on the climate hazard indicators, we refer to Maes et al.³ As additional regressors, we also consider the total number of climate change-attributable deaths due to natural disasters and the climate change-attributable economic damage in a given country and year, as reported by Newman and Noy⁴. However, these measures are zero for most country-year pairings and, unlike pure hazard measures, come with endogeneity issues since climate policy outcomes also determine a country's vulnerability. Therefore, we consider these measures only for robustness checks.

Regression model

We regress average climate policy stringency on linear terms of climate indicators using country and year-fixed effects and country-specific linear time trends, following Rowan⁵, and cluster standard errors by country and year. Results are displayed in Supplementary Table 1. Accounting for the fact that policy output takes time to react to events, all climate indicators are lagged by one year and we explore additional lags as part of our robustness checks (see Supplementary Table 2). Aside from the alternative way of calculating average stringency and the additional control variables, our robustness checks also include limiting the sample only to high-income countries (as per World Bank definitions) or to middle-income countries (low-income countries do not feature in the CAPMF sample). Across all robustness checks, average climate policy stringency exhibits no statistically significant relationship with annual precipitation, extreme precipitation, extreme heat, wildfire exposure, or climate change-attributable deaths and damages. For soil moisture change as a measure of potential drought,

some specifications indicate a statistically significant link. However, the sign of the effect varies across model specifications and is not economically significant, given that even the 2012 US drought from our case studies (see Figure 2b) would affect policy stringency by less than +/- 0.01 (on a scale from zero to ten). Furthermore, annual mean temperature shows a significant negative link with policy stringency if additional lags are introduced (see Supplementary Table 3). While this could potentially reflect adverse impacts on economic growth, effect sizes for a +1°C shock remain small.

We control for annual temperature and precipitation because these measures can have strong correlations with the respective extremes. For instance, the 2003 heatwave in France also coincides with a notable spike in annual temperature. As annual temperature and precipitation have been linked to various socio-economic outcomes, such as economic growth^{6,7}, we include these measures as controls to ensure that we do not falsely attribute the impacts of these variables to correlated measures of climate extremes.

Note that, in our main specification, we use purely climatic indicators for climate extremes, rather than outcomes of climate extremes like casualties or economic damages, due to endogeneity concerns. While year-to-year variations in climatic extremes are plausibly near-random, their outcomes strongly depend not just on hazards but also on exposure and vulnerability⁸. The latter two are strongly affected by domestic policy and other factors, which may introduce reverse causality issues and omitted variable bias.

Supplementary Table 1

Dependent Variables: Model:	Stringency mean (0-10)		Alt. average (0-10)		Stringency mean (0-10)			
	Main (1)	Alt. DV (2)	High-income (3)	Non-high-income (4)	+ Attr. CC Impacts (5)	+ Wildfire (6)	Alt. Heat (7)	Alt. Heat 2 (8)
<i>Variables</i>								
Annual temperature change (°C)	-0.0252 (0.0176)	-0.0288 (0.0196)	-0.0192 (0.0178)	-0.0834 (0.0683)	-0.0250 (0.0177)	-0.0089 (0.0258)	-0.0266 (0.0178)	-0.0209 (0.0188)
Share of land exposed to extreme precipitation (%)	-0.0002 (0.0006)	-0.0003 (0.0006)	-0.0002 (0.0006)	0.0014 (0.0025)	-0.0002 (0.0006)	-4.16×10^{-5} (0.0008)	-0.0002 (0.0006)	-0.0002 (0.0006)
# of days w/ very strong heat stress	0.0023 (0.0031)	0.0022 (0.0031)	-0.0011 (0.0040)	-0.0005 (0.0037)	0.0024 (0.0030)	0.0054 (0.0034)		
Annual precipitation change (dm)	-0.0025 (0.0047)	-0.0052 (0.0035)	-0.0003 (0.0062)	0.0132 (0.0148)	-0.0025 (0.0046)	-0.0087 (0.0081)	-0.0023 (0.0050)	-0.0039 (0.0048)
Soil moisture change (%)	0.0013 (0.0018)	0.0014 (0.0017)	0.0015 (0.0015)	-0.0135* (0.0067)	0.0013 (0.0018)	0.0035 (0.0030)	0.0013 (0.0016)	0.0009 (0.0018)
CC-attributed deaths					-3.44×10^{-6} (2.57×10^{-6})			
CC-attributed damages (USDm)					-7.42×10^{-7} (1.07×10^{-6})			
Population exposed to very high or extreme wildfire danger (%)						0.0052 (0.0039)		
# of days with very high temperature							0.0007 (0.0010)	
# of hot summer days (over 35°C)								-0.0004 (0.0005)
<i>Fixed-effects</i>								
iso	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
year	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
<i>Varying Slopes</i>								
year (iso)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
<i>Fit statistics</i>								
Observations	1,620	1,620	1,268	352	1,620	1,120	1,620	1,620
R ²	0.977	0.975	0.979	0.967	0.977	0.973	0.977	0.977
Within R ²	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.027	0.003	0.007	0.003	0.003
BIC	929.8	1,095.1	697.3	233.2	943.8	867.8	930.0	929.9

Clustered (iso & year) standard-errors in parentheses

Signif. Codes: ***: 0.01, **: 0.05, *: 0.1

Supplementary Table 2

Dependent Variable:	Stringency mean (0-10)			
	+ 2nd lag	+ 3rd lag	Only 2nd lag	Only 3rd lag
Model:	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
<i>Variables</i>				
Annual temperature change (°C)	-0.0242 (0.0185)	-0.0253 (0.0188)		
L2: Annual temperature change (°C)	-0.0310 (0.0211)	-0.0279 (0.0233)	-0.0302 (0.0205)	
Share of land exposed to extreme precipitation (%)	-0.0001 (0.0006)	-0.0001 (0.0006)		
L2: Share of land exposed to extreme precipitation (%)	-0.0005 (0.0004)	-0.0004 (0.0004)	-0.0005 (0.0003)	
# of days w/ very strong heat stress	0.0018 (0.0030)	0.0023 (0.0032)		
L2: # of days w/ very strong heat stress	0.0005 (0.0031)	7.98×10^{-5} (0.0030)	0.0005 (0.0030)	
Annual precipitation change (dm)	-0.0014 (0.0045)	-0.0020 (0.0048)		
L2: Annual precipitation change (dm)	-0.0126* (0.0062)	-0.0123* (0.0061)	-0.0132** (0.0064)	
Soil moisture change (%)	0.0012 (0.0016)	0.0014 (0.0018)		
L2: Soil moisture change (%)	0.0028 (0.0020)	0.0029 (0.0019)	0.0031 (0.0022)	
L3: Annual temperature change (°C)		-0.0396** (0.0185)		-0.0370* (0.0194)
L3: Share of land exposed to extreme precipitation (%)		0.0005 (0.0004)		0.0006 (0.0004)
L3: # of days w/ very strong heat stress		0.0037 (0.0033)		0.0035 (0.0033)
L3: Annual precipitation change (dm)		-0.0039 (0.0049)		-0.0043 (0.0047)
L3: Soil moisture change (%)		0.0013 (0.0023)		0.0020 (0.0026)
<i>Fixed-effects</i>				
iso	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
year	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
<i>Varying Slopes</i>				
year (iso)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
<i>Fit statistics</i>				
Observations	1,569	1,518	1,569	1,518
R ²	0.977	0.977	0.977	0.976
Within R ²	0.011	0.017	0.008	0.008
BIC	958.6	983.4	925.5	925.2

Clustered (iso & year) standard-errors in parentheses

Signif. Codes: ***: 0.01, **: 0.05, *: 0.1

SI-Section C: Case studies on post-disaster policy developments for climate mitigation and adaptation across three countries

We employed a most-likely case selection strategy, operating on the assumption that if severe climate extremes influence climate policymaking, their effects should be observable in cases of extraordinary extreme weather events. By focusing on cases where the impact on policymaking is expected to be most pronounced, we argue that a lack of clear effects in such extreme cases suggests a weak or nonexistent causal link between climate extremes and policy change. To select cases, we used data on climate change-attributable economic damages and mortality provided by Newman and Noy⁴, excluding hazards not directly associated with climate change, i.e., (i) earthquakes caused by ground movement and (ii) tsunamis. Finally, we selected three case studies, ensuring geographical diversity and compatibility with the CAPMF database on climate mitigation policy stringency. This approach allowed for robust analysis of the potential connections between extreme weather events and policy changes. Specifically, we focused our case studies on France that experienced a record heatwave in 2003, which resulted in more than 19,000 deaths. India experienced damaging floods in 2013, with more than a US\$ 1 billion in total damages and more than half a million people affected, while the United States experienced a serious drought event in 2012, leading to more than US\$ 22 billion in total damages.

Unlike for mitigation policy, there is no leading database for adaptation policies and no framework assessing adaptation policy stringency in a consistent and harmonized way. Therefore, for our illustrative case studies and descriptive evidence depicted in Figure 2d of the manuscript, we instead use a policy density measure for adaptation, defined as the cumulative number of adopted adaptation policies, based on two different databases. The first source is the Climate Change Laws of the World database maintained by the London School of Economics and Political Science, which collects national-level laws, policies, and UNFCCC documents and assigns them to four different topics (i.e., mitigation, adaptation, disaster risk management, and loss and damage)⁹. Notably, the database only features documents with full legal force and groups documents that belong to the same policy into so-called 'families'. For more information, see <https://climate-laws.org/methodology>. We calculate adaptation policy density as a country's cumulative number of policies and laws assigned to the Adaptation topic published through the year in question. When doing so, we count document families instead of documents to avoid double-counting documents belonging to the same policy or law. We exclude UNFCCC documents as they are not necessarily policies and are not assigned a topic in the database.

Second, we use the Climate Policy Database (Version 2023) maintained by NewClimate Institute, which tracks laws, targets, strategic documents, and other policy documents related to climate policy for 42 countries^{10,11}. Different policy objectives, such as 'Mitigation,' 'Air pollution,' or 'Adaptation,' are assigned to each policy. For more information, see <https://climatepolicydatabase.org/methodology>. We calculate adaptation policy density as a

country's cumulative number of database entries with Adaptation as a policy objective that have been decided through the year in question. When doing so, we do not take into account if the policy continues to be in place or has been removed or superseded.

France has positioned itself among the top countries for climate policy stringency, implementing various climate mitigation policies over the past decades. France increased its climate mitigation policy efforts after the 2003 heatwave, notably with improvements in the electricity sector. The adoption of the Emissions Trading System (ETS) in 2005 and stricter air emission standards were key developments, aiming to curb greenhouse gas emissions from the growing demand for air conditioning after the devastating heatwave¹². These initiatives were part of the 2004 French Climate Plan, which also included measures to ensure reliable electricity supply during extreme weather events. However, it is unclear whether there is a causal link between the 2003 heatwave and the increasing climate mitigation stringency in France. Other factors, such as party politics, technological innovation and industrial policy motives, could be important explanations for the change in climate mitigation stringency¹³. In the case of adaptation policy making, France has progressively advanced its climate resilience strategies. In 2006, the French national adaptation strategy was introduced, addressing public health, inequalities, and natural heritage preservation¹⁴. The national adaptation strategy frequently cites the 2003 heatwave, noting *'it will correspond to "normal" summers by the end of the 21st century'*. It also emphasizes that *'the poorest and most vulnerable were the first to suffer'*, underscoring the need to adapt to a changing climate. This was followed by the first Plan national d'adaptation au changement climatique (PNACC) in 2011¹⁵, updated in 2018 with PNACC-2¹⁶, aiming to adapt to a 2°C global temperature rise by 2050. Meanwhile, the number of subnational adaptation policies has also grown considerably. Between 2007 and 2017, for example, 16 local adaptation plans have been identified for small and mid-size communities in France¹⁷. Currently, a third national adaptation plan is being developed, incorporating a more pessimistic scenario of 4°C warming by 2100, reflecting the challenges in reducing emissions¹⁸.

India's average climate mitigation stringency levels over the past two decades are comparable to OECD partner countries, but lower than OECD member countries. In the late 2010s, India's climate mitigation policy mix captured by the CAPMF became more stringent, mainly driven by increased international climate policy ambition. While it is difficult to establish a causal link between these national mitigation efforts and the flood disaster in 2013, a clearer connection can be made for local post-disaster policy changes. The Indian State's Uttarakhand Action Plan for Climate Change (UAPCC) explicitly mentions the 2013 flood disaster, stating that it *'has several lessons to be learnt!'*. In December 2013, approval of UAPCC by the State Council of Climate Change presided by the Chief Secretary with instructions to incorporate changes in the context of the flood. While the plan entails an analysis of the disaster, it also states that the flood raised a new issue of the role of big hydropower projects in contributing to natural disasters, suggesting a potential negative effect of the flood on increased climate mitigation efforts¹⁹. India integrated climate adaptation into its policy framework with the 2008 National Action Plan on Climate Change (NAPCC)²⁰. This

plan introduced eight national missions, jointly focusing on climate mitigation and adaptation, such as the National Water Mission, the National Mission for Sustainable Agriculture, and the National Mission for Sustaining the Himalayan Ecosystem. These missions aimed to address regional sustainability and promote coordination between the Union Government and state governments, particularly for managing river basins and developing sustainable agriculture. In 2018, India introduced the National Action Plan on Climate Change and Human Health (NAPCCHH), expanding its scope with four new missions, including the Health Mission, to address health impacts of climate change, such as the rise in vector-borne diseases²¹. Each state was encouraged to create its own State Action Plan for Climate Change and Human Health (SAPCCHH), adapting strategies to regional challenges.

The **United States** increased its mitigation policy stringency in several sectors after the 2012 drought according to the CAPMF data. This is notably the case for transport, electricity, industry and international policies. However, it is difficult to identify a causal link between this increased mitigation effort and the drought event. Local governments made reference to the drought in their climate change analysis and discussed impacts on crops, livestock and fisheries^{22,23} but little to no reference is made to concrete policy implications. The 2012 drought event is also not mentioned in any national climate mitigation policy document, potentially caused by the lack of media coverage connecting the event to climate change²⁴. While the specific drought event cannot be linked to the increased mitigation efforts, research shows that health concerns, especially the negative impacts of extreme heat and weather events for low-income families, were an important motivator for the development of climate policies during the Obama administration between 2008 and 2016²⁵.

In terms of adaptation policy, the link to the 2012 drought is more obvious. The US Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) issued its first Policy Statement on Climate Change Adaptation in 2011²⁶. Ever since, the agency has been actively integrating climate considerations into its activities. The EPA has released five climate change adaptation plans, all of which frequently refer to the drought. The first Climate Change Adaptation Plan in 2012 mentioned that *'the Southwest is in the midst of a 10-15-year drought, and [...] it may transition to a more arid climate on a permanent basis over the next century'*²⁷. The US drought disaster of 2012 encompassed the Southwest and most of the Midwest²⁸, highlighting how the EPA's adaptation plans refer to the 2012 drought and other disasters. The EPA has released five climate change adaptation plans, with the latest plans in 2021²⁹ and in 2024³⁰, emphasizing the urgency of addressing climate change³¹. The 2021 Climate Adaptation Action Plan²⁹ identifies vulnerabilities in five key areas: air quality, water quality, contaminated sites, chemical safety and pollution prevention, and the EPA's own facilities and operations. It highlights how climate-induced factors like rising temperatures and increased wildfires can elevate ozone and particulate matter levels, escalating risks of respiratory illnesses and premature deaths, especially among vulnerable populations. Overall, these policies represent a comprehensive effort by the EPA to protect human health and the environment by fully integrating climate adaptation into its programs, policies, and operations.

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